

Research Article

A revised typification of *Cyathea jacobsii* and a new combination in *Sphaeropteris* (Cyatheaceae)

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Abstract: A new combination is made for *Cyathea x lathamii* Holttum under the genus *Sphaeropteris* Bernh. as *S. x lathamii* (Holttum) Deroliya, Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr.Singh. The current neotype of *Cyathea jacobsii* Holttum is incorrect according to Article 9.13 of the ICN, as syntypes are extant at L. The specimen at L (L1259840) is designated as the lectotype for the name *C. jacobsii* Holttum and will supersede the previous neotypification.

Keywords: *Cyathea x lathamii*, Indonesia, Lectotype, Malaysia, Tree fern

Introduction

The tree fern genus *Sphaeropteris* Bernh. consists of about 107 species, distributed in Australia, Indian subcontinent, South China to Southeast Asia, South Pacific and New Zealand, and only a few species occur in tropical America (POWO, 2025; Singh, 2025). In Indonesia, the genus is represented by 48 species (Singh, 2025). However, the hybrid taxon *Cyathea x lathamii* Holttum needs to be transferred to the genus *Sphaeropteris* Bernh. Therefore, following recent circumscription of *Sphaeropteris*, a new combination is proposed here for *Cyathea x lathamii* under the genus *Sphaeropteris* as *S. x lathamii* (Holttum) Deroliya, Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr.Singh. The neotype (L0051305) of *Cyathea jacobsii* Holttum designated by Singh (2025) is equivocal according to Article 9.13 of the ICN (Turland et al., 2018) as original material are extant. After thorough consultation of K and L virtual herbarium, we found four original specimens for *Cyathea jacobsii* Holttum, but in the name *C. tripinnata* Copel.

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Cyathea jacobsonii* Holttum (L1259840, © Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden)

Figure 2: Isolectotype of *Cyathea jacobsii* Holttum (L1259839, © Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden)

Therefore, following the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of ICN (Turland et al., 2018), the specimen at L (L1259840) is designated as the lectotype for the name *C. jacobsii* Holttum and will supersede the previous neotypification.

Nomenclature

Sphaopteris × lathamii (Holttum) Deroliya, Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Cyathea × lathamii* Holttum, Amer. Fern J. 74: 20. 1984.

Type: Cultivated in the Birmingham Botanical Gardens, England, 9 July 1890, *W.B. Latham* (K).

Hybrid Parentage: *Sphaopteris excelsa* (R.Br. ex Endl.) R.M.Tryon [≡ *Cyathea brownii* Domin] × *Sphaopteris horrida* (Liebm.) R.M.Tryon [= *Cyathea princeps* (W.Bull ex J.Dix) E.Mayer bis 1868, *nom. illeg., non C. princeps* J.Sm. 1866].

Distribution: Cultivated in the Birmingham Botanical Gardens, England (Holttum, 1984).

Sphaopteris jacobsii (Holttum) R.Kr.Singh, J. Biodivers. Conservation 9(1): 64. 2025.

≡ *Cyathea jacobsii* Holttum, Reinwardtia 8: 499. 1974. *C. tripinnata sensu* Holttum in Fl. Males., Ser. 2, Pterid. 1: 140. 1963, *p.p.*, [*non* Copel., Philipp. J. Sci. 1(Suppl. 4): 251. 1906].

Lectotype (designated here): Indonesia, Sumatra, Province of Lampung, Tanggamus, 1200–1300 m, 28 April 1968, *M. Jacobs 8113* (L1259840!, Figure 1); isolectotypes L1259839! (Figure 2), K000706396, K000706397.

Distribution: Indonesia and Malaysia.

Notes: Holttum (1974) mentioned the type in L and duplicates in BO and K. Our search for the type of *Cyathea jacobsii* Holttum at L, we could able to locate two specimens (L1259840 and L1259839). We also traced two more specimens at K (K000706396 and K000706397). Among the two specimens at L herbarium, the specimen L1259840 being the best-preserved and most fitting the protologue description, is designated here as the lectotype.

Acknowledgements

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